

Coffee By-Product Valorisation

Coffee by-products such as cascara, coffee leaves or alcohol made from fermented coffee materials, have been traditionally used in some coffee-producing countries. While the beans have been the major commodity, by-products have not typically reached the importing countries and often need regulatory approval. Coffee by-products may be an interesting addition to the value chain.

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All images courtesy of Dr Dirk W Lachenmeier and Dr Steffen Schwarz

The most well-known coffee by-product is cascara, from the Spanish word *cáscara*, meaning husk, which are the dried cherries from which the seeds (coffee beans) have been removed. Interestingly, despite the Spanish word being commonly used worldwide for coffee husk or its derived beverage, the authors have not observed any traditional use of cascara in Latin America, but it has been commonly consumed in Yemen (called qishr) and Ethiopia (called hashara), per *A Review of Coffee By-Products Including Leaf, Flower, Cherry, Husk, Silver Skin, and Spent Grounds as Novel Foods within the European Union*, Foods 2020, 9, 665. (<https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9050665>). This article focuses on the lesser-known by-products with food uses, including spirits (alcoholic distillates) and tea-like drinks.

Novel Spirits with Coffee By-Products: Observations in Nepal

Sindhupalchok, Nepal is a beautiful hill region on the foothills of Jugal Mountain with an elevation ranging from 300 meters to 7,080 meters, felicitous for coffee farming. To promote coffee farming, a coffee cooperative was established in 2013, which now has more than 2,400 active smallholder farmer members and groups. Almost all the members have their own coffee plants ranging from five to 500 plants.

Interestingly in recent times, some of the members of the coffee cooperatives are also engaged in making artisanal spirits – more

commonly recognised in local terms as *Kodo ko Rakshi* (alcohol made from millet). The spirits have an important part of local culture, religious ceremonies, rituals, festivals and daily life. Despite some alcohol-related problems, positive impacts of alcohol production may be linked with women's economic empowerment. It provides solid cash earning opportunities for women as they are the ones who are directly engaged in sorting, fermenting and production while their male counterparts engage in other work for sustaining their livelihoods.

Socioeconomic research was conducted with smallholder farmers from Karki Tar village of Sindhupalchok, Nepal. Making alcohol using coffee cherry by-products is a new practice adapted during recent times. The research team had four group discussions and observations of making such alcohol.

The cooperative members saw potential for improvement of the flavour and taste of spirits using dried skins of coffee cherries (cascara including some residues of parchment from natural processing). Cascara is now popular for tea preparation, as well. Talking to women who were engaged in making alcohol, insights on the process of making millet or rice spirits and adding coffee by-products were obtained. After cleaning the grains, they need to be well cooked, similar to a standard rice preparation. After cooling down, the boiled cascara is added and then left for some time so that the flavour transfers into the cooked grain millet or rice.

Another important material is *marcha* (made with herbal plants and works like yeast), which is used for fermentation. Boiled cascara with cooked millet or rice is kept for up to a week, and then it is ready to distill the alcohol. The utensils play an important role in this process, which are *bata* (deep utensil for holding water), *petashi* that holds *nani* for collecting alcohol and *foshi*, which is directly exposed with heat and holds the fermented mixture. In this process, fire plays an important role, as the millet or rice mixed *marcha* needs to be cooked for a long time, and the water needs to be boiled several times. The total time starts from three hours at least, and even more depending on the potency of the alcohol.

The fire is lit, and *foshi* is kept on it, which holds millet or rice mixed coffee flavoured *marcha*. On its open end, *petashi* is tightly fitted with the help of wet cloths. Inside *petashi*, remains *nani* (used for collecting alcohol). On top, *bata*, which is filled with water, is installed airtight. With the exposure to heat, the millet or rice mixed *marcha* evaporates

after heating with boiling water collected in *bata*. This is when the alcohol in tiny droplets, in local terms dubbed as *pashina* (translation: sweat) gets collected in *nani*. Once the mixture is fully evaporated, water is instantly replaced.

This is how the alcoholic strength is controlled. The less water is replaced, the higher is the strength of the alcohol. The first collection of alcohol, which consists of just tiny droplets (around 100 ml) are potent enough to ignite fire and have a burning hot taste. For a standard level, the water is changed six times, giving it the name *six pane*. Some people even demand *tin pane* (water replace three times) as the alcohol level is more highly concentrated – making it more valuable in the market. Due to the addition of coffee by-products, it has a unique taste; some people also claim certain medicinal properties such as alleviating bodily pain and seasonal flu, coughs or colds. The demand for this spirit has increased, and even at a governmental level, the exploitation for international marketing is currently being considered.

Traditional Uses of Coffee Leaves

The leaves of the coffee plant have been used for a long time to prepare tea-like drinks. In West Sumatra, Ethiopia, Yemen, Jamaica, India, Java and South Sudan, the infusion is consumed as a traditional food. Before preparing the drink, there are different processing methods to obtain coffee leaf tea. Most of them include leaf steaming, rolling and drying.

However, some manufacturers work under a protective gas atmosphere to preserve the ingredients from oxidation. Alternatively, the

▷ Coffee husks

(Left) Silver skins (Right) Coffee husks

leaves can also be fermented. In some production methods, the drying process is supplemented by a roasting process. To produce a drink, the tea must be extracted with water according to the aforementioned article, *A Review of Coffee By-Products Including Leaf, Flower, Cherry, Husk, Silver Skin, and Spent Grounds as Novel Foods within the European Union*.

Novel Food Regulations in the European Union

According to Regulation (EU) 2015/2283, only novel foods that have been approved and included on the European Union list may be placed on the

market in the EU. Traditional foods from a third country are also considered novel foods. In the Implementing regulation (EU) 2020/917 of the Commission of 1 July 2020, the placing on the market of infusion from coffee leaves of *Coffea arabica* L and/or *Coffea canephora* Pierre ex A Froehner as a traditional food from a third country was authorised as the first coffee by-products.

The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) had set a maximum level of 700 mg epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG) per litre infusion prior to approval but had not expressed any other safety concerns (see *Technical Report on the Notification of Infusion from Coffee Leaves [Coffea*

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The following conditions, among others, were attached to the approval: the designation of the novel food on the labelling of the foodstuffs containing it shall be 'Infusion from coffee leaves of *Coffea arabica* and/or *Coffea canephora*.' The traditional food is prepared by mixing a maximum of 20g of dried leaves from *Coffea arabica* L and/or *Coffea canephora* Pierre ex A Froehner with one litre of hot water. Leaves are removed and the infusion is then subjected to pasteurisation (at least 71°C for 15 seconds).

Maximum contents are among others: Chlorogenic acid (5-CQA): < 100 mg/L, caffeine: < 80 mg/L, epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG): < 700 mg/L (see the Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2020/917 of 1 July 2020 authorising the placing on the market of infusion from coffee leaves of *Coffea arabica* L and/or *Coffea canephora* Pierre ex A Froehner as a traditional food from a third country under Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 of the European Parliament and of the Council and amending Implementing Regulation (EU) 2017/2470. OJ L 209, 2.7.2020, pages 10–13, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg_impl/2020/917/oj, for complete specifications).

No systematic data of chemical composition of spirits made from coffee by-products is currently available. Concerns were raised about a comparably high methanol content of pure coffee cherry spirits (Blumenthal, P; Steger, MC; Einfalt, D; Rieke-Zapp, J; Quintanilla Bellucci, A; Sommerfeld, K; Schwarz, S; Lachenmeier, DW *Methanol Mitigation During Manufacturing of Fruit Spirits With Special Consideration of Novel Coffee Cherry Spirits*. Preprints 2021, 2021030731, [https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202103.0731.v1.](https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202103.0731.v1))

However, in the case of the spirits from Nepal, this problem appears already mitigated by the admixture of grain materials, which are low in methanol formation capability.

Conclusions

Especially against the background of the economic crisis caused by Covid-19, it is very welcome that coffee leaf tea is now the first coffee by-product to receive EU approval. An increase in the added value of the coffee plant could increase the social and economic prosperity in poorer coffee-growing areas and counteract decreasing coffee prices.

(Top) Tea made from coffee flowers.
(Bottom) Coffee leaf tea

Approval procedures for other coffee by-products such as cascara (coffee cherry) are still ongoing or have yet to be initiated (for blossom and pulp, as well as for coffee cherry-based alcohol, refer to *A Review of Coffee By-Products Including Leaf, Flower, Cherry, Husk, Silver Skin, and Spent Grounds as Novel Foods within the European Union*).

The coffee cherry spirits concept has been tested and seen initial proofs-of-concept in various parts of the world. Though the millet spirit with cascara flavour is a mixed product only partially based on coffee by-products, it is likely to provide a unique taste, with potential to be distinguished from other kinds of spirits.

Exposure and branding are what is needed to give it an international space. ☕

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